

Probabilistic Analysis of Rubble-Mound Berm Breakwaters Considering Correlations Among Environmental Parameters: A Case Study of Tombak Port Breakwater

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**Department of Marine Structures
Faculty of Civil & Environmental Engineering
Tarbiat Modares University**

By:

Ali Jamali Rovesht

Supervisor:

Prof. Mehdi Shafieefar

Advisor:

Dr. Hassan Akbari

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Abstract

Due to the inherent randomness of environmental, hydraulic, and structural parameters, the safe design of rubble-mound berm breakwaters requires probabilistic approaches and reliability-based analyses. This study presents a comprehensive probabilistic assessment of rubble-mound berm breakwaters, emphasizing the influence of correlations and interactions among environmental variables. The primary objective was to evaluate failure probabilities over the service life of the structure by exploring different dependency structures among environmental parameters and assessing available empirical formulas for two major failure modes: berm recession and overtopping. Four dependency structures—independence, Gaussian copula, Frank copula, and D-vine copula—were used to model parameter correlations. Reliability assessment was conducted using FORM, SORM, and Importance Sampling methods, with performance compared against benchmark Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) results. A case study on the rubble-mound berm breakwater at Tombak Port employed multiple empirical formulas for both berm recession and overtopping failure modes. Results demonstrated that, under the D-vine structure, the Torum (2007) formula yielded the lowest failure probability (28.9%), while Hall and Kao (1991) reported the highest (72.01%) for berm recession. Correlation structures significantly influenced outcomes, with a maximum observed difference in failure probability of 4.94%. For overtopping, five empirical formulas were analyzed, with Van der Meer and Janssen (1994) showing the lowest failure probability (27.99%) and Van der Meer and Sigurdarson (2012) the highest (69.56%), while the remaining formulas produced results between 45% and 67%.

Sensitivity analysis using the FORM method showed that wave height and wave period are generally the most significant load parameters, while the density and mass of the armor layer stones are the most critical resistance parameters. Moreover, considering the correlation between environmental parameters brings the order of importance closer to physical reality and highlights that accounting for correlations and the statistical characteristics of variables is essential when assessing failure probability.

Keywords: Probabilistic analysis, reliability, rubble-mound berm breakwater, copula, berm recession, overtopping, correlation.